

2-Substituted-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones as Possible Anticonvulsants

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Twentyone new 2-(*N*¹-substituted-phenylthiourea-*N*²-yl)/(substituted-phenylthiocarbamate) / [2-(substituted-phenylimino)thiazolid-4-one-3-yl] / [(3-mercapto-4-substituted-phenyl-1, 2, 4(*H*)-triazol-5-yl)methylamino/methyleneoxy]-5-chloro / nitrobenzophenones were synthesised and screened for their acute toxicity, effect on gross behaviour and anticonvulsant activity against electroshock and metrazole induced seizures. However, none of the compounds tested showed any significant activity at 1/10th of the LD₅₀ which suggested that an incorporation of thiourea, thiocarbamate, thiazolidone or mercapto-triazole moiety into active 2-amino/hydroxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones may result in a loss of their activity.

1-Phenyl-1,2,4(*H*)-triazole^{1,2}, triazolines³, mercapto-triazoles⁴, thioureas^{5,6} and thiazolidone⁷ derivatives have exhibited marked anticonvulsant activity. 2-Amino/hydroxybenzophenones are active metabolites⁸ of several anticonvulsant benzodiazepines and some of them had shown anticonvulsant activity against metrazole induced seizures^{9,10}. Further, there had been many reports in which the condensation of two active moieties had led to the compounds with enhanced activity, e.g. imidazole and thiourea¹¹ and oxadiazole and thiazolidone⁷ and benzodiazepine and triazole¹², possibly they have acted on the receptors¹³ sensitive to both of these active groupings. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to incorporate thiourea, thiocarbamate, thiazolidone and mercapto-triazole moieties into 2-amino/hydroxybenzophenones (Scheme 1) and evaluate them for anticonvulsant activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The reactions were followed by the tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord and Perkin-Elmer 177 or 137 grating spectrophotometers. Pmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian A60D spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

2-Amino-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones^{14,15}, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones^{16,17} and 2-*N*-carbethoxymethyl-5-chlorobenzophenones¹⁸ were prepared by the known methods.

Scheme 1

2-(*N*¹-Substituted phenylthiourea-*N*³-yl)/substituted-phenylthiocarbamate-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (4a-h): A mixture of 2-amino/hydroxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenone (0.001 mol), arylisothiocyanate (0.001 mol) and ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 6–10 h. It was then concentrated and the solid product filtered and dried (60–70%), and characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and spectral data, ν_{max} (KBr) ~ 3 300 (sec NH), 1 640 (ArCOAr), 1 605 (Ar), 1 500 and 1 310 (NO₂), and 1 160 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃) of 4c 1.20 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.85 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.25 (2H, m, NH), 6.55–7.15 (12H, m, ArH).

2-[2-(Substituted-phenylimino)thiazolid-4-one-3-yl]-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (5a-f): A mixture of 2-(*N*¹-substituted phenylthiourea-*N*³-yl)-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (4a-h; 0.001 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.001 5 mol) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 10–20 h. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice with stirring and kept overnight at room temperature. The solid thus separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol in 50–60% yields. The compounds were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and spectral data, ν_{max} (KBr) ~ 3 000 (CH₂, aliphatic), 1 730 (amide CO), 1 670 (ArCOAr), 1 645 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (Ar); δ (CDCl₃) of 5c 1.3 (3H, m, CH₃), 2.1 (s, N-C-O-CH₂-S), 3.9 (2H, m, CH₂) and 6.5–7.4 (12H, m, ArH).

2-*N*/O-Carboethoxymethyl-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (6a-c): A mixture of 2-amino/hydroxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (0.001 mol), anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (0.001 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.001 mol) was refluxed for 16–20 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from ethanol, (60–70%). The compounds were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and spectral data.

2-(Hydrazinocarbonyl)methylamino/methyleneoxy-5-chloro-nitrobenzophenones (7a-c): A mixture of 2-*N*/O-carboethoxymethyl-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenone (6a-c; 0.001 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99–100%, 0.001 mol) in absolute ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated in vacuum and separated solid filtered and dried to yield the compounds (60–80%). Compounds were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and spectral data, ν_{max} (KBr) 3 500 and 3 150 (NH hydrazine), 1 720 cm⁻¹ (amide CO), 1 630 (ArCOAr), 1 605 (Ar), 1 520 and 1 300 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

2-(Substituted-phenylthiosemicarbazidocarbonyl)-methylamino/methyleneoxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (8a-g): 2-(Hydrazinocarbonyl)methylamino/methyleneoxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (7a-c; 0.001 mol) and an appropriate arylisothiocyanate

(0.001 mol) were dissolved in dry benzene (20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 6–10 h. The excess benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure. The solid mass which separated on cooling was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (50–60%). The compounds were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and spectral data, ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400–3 150 (NH), 1 710 (amide CO), 1 640 (Ar-CO-Ar), 1 590 (Ar) and 1 170 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

2-[(3-Mercapto-4-substituted-phenyl-1,2,4(H)-triazol-5-yl)methylamino/methyleneoxy]-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones (9a-g): A mixture of an appropriate 2-(substituted-phenylthiosemicarbazidocarbonyl)methylamino/methyleneoxy-5-chloronitrobenzophenone (7a-g; 0.00 mol), sodium methoxide (0.011 mol) and absolute methanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 20–25 h. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was added with stirring to an ice-cold water containing concentrated HCl, resulting a flocculent precipitate of the compound. It was washed successively with water and aqueous 50% acetic acid and finally recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow crystals (40–50%).

The compounds were characterised by the m.p.s., elemental analyses, and ir spectra which showed the disappearance of the peak at 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O of sec amide) present in the corresponding 2-(substituted-phenylthiosemicarbazidocarbonyl)methylamino/methyleneoxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones.

Pharmacological studies: Acute toxicity (LD₅₀ determination)¹⁹, gross behavioural effects²⁰ and anticonvulsant activity²¹ against metrazole and electroshock tests was determined by known procedures⁹.

Results and Discussion

The compounds tested had an LD₅₀ ranging between > 1000–316 mg/kg i.p. (Table 1). The compounds afforded no protection against convulsions induced by metrazole or electroshock in mice nor produced any significant effect on the gross behaviour at 1/5th of the LD₅₀. The absence of activity in the compounds could be due to their inability to act on the receptors on which 2-amino/hydroxybenzophenones act to produce anticonvulsant action. Thus, it may be concluded that an incorporation of thiourea, thiocarbamate, thiazolidone or mercaptotriazole moiety to 2-amino/hydroxy-5-chloro/nitrobenzophenones result in a loss of activity.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	X	R'	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg) i.p. (confidence limit)
4a	Cl	NH	H	150-2	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	-
4b	Cl	NH	Br	220	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrClN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
4c	Cl	NH	OEt	208	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
4d	NO ₂	NH	H	120	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
4e	NO ₂	NH	Br	120	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	681 (nil)
4f	NO ₂	NH	OEt	142-4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
4g	NO ₂	O	Br	102-4	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
4h	NO ₂	O	OEt	145	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
5a	Cl	N	H	155	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	-
5b	Cl	N	Br	195	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrClN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
5c	Cl	N	OEt	145	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	1 000 (642-1 560)
5d	NO ₂	N	H	108	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
5e	NO ₂	N	Br	110	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
5f	NO ₂	N	OEt	120	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
6a	Cl	NH	-	104	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	681 (nil)
6b	NO ₂	NH	-	124-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
6c	NO ₂	O	-	135	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
7a	Cl	NH	-	188	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
7b	NO ₂	NH	-	175	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	316 (nil)
7c	NO ₂	O	-	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
8a	Cl	NH	H	180	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	-
8b	Cl	NH	Cl	188	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
8c	Cl	NH	OEt	158	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	68 (nil)
8d	NO ₂	NH	H	160	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
8e	NO ₂	NH	OEt	125-8	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
8f	NO ₂	O	Cl	165-7	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	1 000 (642-1 560)
8g	NO ₂	O	OEt	180	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
9a	Cl	NH	H	195-7	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	-
9b	Cl	NH	Cl	210	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
9c	Cl	NH	OEt	180-2	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
9d	NO ₂	NH	H	202-4	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	464 (298-723)
9e	NO ₂	NH	OEt	140-2	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	-
9f	NO ₂	O	Cl	180-2	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	>1 000
9g	NO ₂	O	OEt	210	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	-

*Elemental analyses are consistent with the composition. At 1/5th of LD₅₀, compounds showed no effect on gross behaviour and exhibited on protection against metrazole or electroshock seizures.

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